

Strategic Planning Efforts: An Assessment of Tripoli University Performance¹

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Article Type: Review Article

Received: 28.09.2022

Vol 4 (Issue 2) 2022: 18-34

Revised: 07.11.2022

 10.5281/zenodo.7434136

Accepted: 11.11.2022

Cite as: Aboudaber, A. (2022). Strategic Planning Efforts: An Assessment of Tripoli University Performance. *Quantrade Journal of Complex Systems in Social Sciences*, 4 (2) , 18-34. Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7434136

Abstract

The study explores the impact of strategic planning to achieve recommendations that improve efficiency and effectiveness in tertiary institutions in Libya. The study was carried out exclusively on employees at the University of Tripoli. The importance of this study stems, in particular, from its academic and professional contributions, to the universities of Tripoli. The study favored descriptive and analytical approaches that provide a deeper insight into what's going to happen in the future and give more accurate, reliable results than pure analysis. A total of 458 executives and staff, including faculties and institutes at the University of Tripoli, make up the research's universe. In this work, participants are identified by the sampling method. After examining each subdimension of strategic planning independently with the University of Tripoli's performance level, significant differences were found for the following two variables. These sub-dimensions can be sorted by strategic analysis and strategic selection. At the University of Tripoli's performance level, no significant differences were found for the following sub-dimensions. These can be sorted by strategic vision, mission and objectives. Finally, because of the academic competency variables and the current business area, it has been found that there are statistically significant differences in participants' positions on strategic planning level, and that participants' positions on demographic data and performance concepts have been statistically differentiated based on existing business area variables.

Keywords: Strategic Planning, University of Tripoli, Higher Education Performance

1. Introduction

The study considers the fruitful work of Tripoli University, the largest university in Libya, to give to strategic planning. The university has the largest number of Libyan students in the region. The University of Tripoli was founded in 1957, and it is an institution with a total of 4,000 employees and 3,000 academics, and faculties with many different disciplines, home to 100,000 students.

For all these reasons, this work is particularly important in higher education institutions as an incentive to demonstrate the importance of strategic planning for the development of educational activities and a higher quality for the education sector. The primary objective of the study is to determine the extent to which factors are involved in strategic planning are effective on performance. It is also about enabling the positive and negative aspects of the University of Tripoli to be established through long-term strategic planning. It is believed that this work could serve as the basis for much work to be done in the future.

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2.Literature

In strategic management, classical scholars include Ansoff' (1965), Penrose (1959), Chandler (1962), Rumelt (1997) and Porter (1990, 1991). Scientists who advocate for classical understanding have mainly treated the strategy as the firm's competitive strategy. Ansoff (1965) described the strategy as relevant to the relationship between the firm and its surroundings. The same scientist sees institutional strategy as a process by which executives can anticipate future challenges due to the organization's environment and hence determine intervention plans. He also argues that strategic planning is a must-have part of the organization. One of the classical thinkers, Sofia's strategy view (1965), was criticized by Ansoff and McDonnell (1990) for not taking into account the unpredictable environment where he thought events were predictable, and that unpredictable events might develop. After this criticism, these environments were described as "Turbulent Environment". Another view of Sofia (1965) is that strategic thinking can be decoupled from institutional management. Finally, Sofia said that new strategies can be developed with the techniques of data analysis (Mintzberg, 1994). It is important to remember that Ansoff's theories were also criticized. The main reason for criticism is that there is no evidence that Ansoff's theories can be applied to small organizations. Only large institutions have been investigated and small institutions not included (Kiple, 2009; Mintzberg, 1990). The top-down strategic planning process, or hierarchical strategic planning process, is said to provide very little input to small organizations. As a plan, the strategy refers to leaders' organization and employees' familiarization with a predetermined manner of action. That's why leaders are more interested in trying to lead the organization. Such a strategy is intended (Mintzberg v., 1996).

The strategy can also be seen by scientists or as a learning process (e.g., Starkey, 1996), or as a flow of activity (Mintzberg and Waters, 1985). Mintzberg and Quinn (1996) also called the strategy "a pattern strategy". From a perspective towards the strategy, one can see that it is a unified way of perceiving the world surrounding institutions. It is shared by members of the organization through intentions and/or actions. From the point of view of the board's members, strategy is the way the organization will go about getting there, with the vision and goals it wishes to be. However, it has also contributed to understanding how the organization will develop over time (Mintzberg and Quinn, 1996). Strategies may be intended, realized, exposed, intentional or unrealized (Mintzberg, 1994; Rumelt, 2011).

If the implementation of a intended strategy can proceed as planned, it has turned into a deliberate strategy. A strategy has been described as a stream of decisions that are regularly exhibited as time goes on (Mintzberg, 1978). An unrealized strategy appears in situations where the strategy evolves, although it is not intended, but with certain intentions. The strategy appears over time as it adapts to intentions (Moore, 2011, Mintzberg, and Waters, 1985). An organization can perform a series of activities that, over time, become a consistent pattern of behavior when there are no intentions. The resulting and continuous patterns become strategies (Mintzberg, 1994, Mintzberg and Quinn, 1996). Recent research in strategic management has seen more and more of the processes of organizational learning, rather than the effective policy-making processes of emerging strategies (Klijin, 2008) The strategic perspective as practice focuses on ways in which strategy practitioners are activated or restricted by organizational, social practices (Johnson, and., 2008). The question of which is better in strategic management is the subject of ongoing debate. Advocates of formalized strategic planning include Steiner (1999), while Mintzberg (1993) Quinn and Voyer (1998) advocated for unformalized strategic planning. In his study, Ansoff (1965) considered strategy building and development to be a process that had to be conducted in a conscious way. Lindblom (1959) argued that public sector officials should base their decisions on limited knowledge, policy analysis and rationality, and that decision-making should be fragmented. Lindblom (1959) also claimed that strategic decision-making was not a truly coordinated and rational process. Some other authors argue that strategic decision-making, such as Ansoff, (1965), Mintzberg, and Quinn (1996), is a planned process. Pettigrew (1985) argued that decision-making was not always rational,

but that rationality could exist when the actor included his own interests. He also stated that the strategic decision-making process was influenced by bureaucracy, organizational structure and environmental factors. Finally, he claimed that strategizing was a political process (Pettigrew, 1977). According to Bryson (2004), strategic planning in the public sector ranges from individual public institutions to governments, and their specific functions, such as transportation, organization, government, and inter-organization networks. The relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance was also criticized for being uncertain (Mintzberg, 1994; Grant, 2003; Poster, etc.). Some research also highlighted the importance of effective and efficient management and the importance of the organization having flexible bureaucracy (Meier and O'Toole, 2009).

According to a study by Moore (1997), administrators should continually educate themselves, constantly questioning what they can produce, how they can meet citizens' demands, and how they can network with their political auditors (Moore, 2010).

To summarize, strategies are closely related to the organization and its environment, to governance, to objectives, to organizational aspects, and to strategizing. So the definition of strategy is related to how and why the organization uses it. In organizations, the concept of institutional strategy was first described in the 2009 financial statement (Ministry of Interior, 2010b) as follows, the common strategic objectives of the administration sector and actions to implement them. The strategy guides activities and financial planning and strengthens public sector procedures in performance measurements. The concept of an institutional strategy is to guide actions and see activities as a controllable process (Quinn and Voyer, 1998).

At the same time, strategies are all decisions and actions towards common goals. It is also closely associated with performance management. The strategic implementation described above is a targeted strategy (Mintzberg and Quinn, 1996). In recent research on the development process and challenges of the public sector, complexity theory has been preferred. The theorem involved has been considered a possibility to explore the organizational development process and solve complex problems that arise (Head, 2008; Klijin, 2008; Mitleton-Kelly, 2003; MacIntosh, etc., 2006; Klijin, 2008). Further information on the subject is included in a 2003 study by Mitleton and Kelly, or in a 2006 study by MacIntosh, etc. In complexity theory, strategies are not shaped by unilateral responses to a changing environment, but by the actions and interactions of different actors in the networks (Klijin, 2008; Mitleton and Kelly, 2003). Complex systems consist of many interactive parts according to rules, laws, or forces (Maguire and McKelvey, 1999).

In self-sustaining organizations, actors interact dynamically and reshape the environment (Bovaird, 2008; Stahle, 2008). Adaptability of actors to the system is an important factor in success (Stahle, 2008; Bovaird, 2008). Elections, events, activity, and the positions of actors are shaped. Following the position, the manager's job is to assess opportunities, develop policy recommendations or adapt plans to suit the circumstances of the moment (Klijin, 2008). According to the ideology of anarchism, organizations are not well-organized rational systems, but systems in which individual solutions, problems, and events must be connected (Klijin, 2008; Cohen and., 1972). Self-organization is self-reforming and capable of complex decision-making (Klijin, 2008; Stahle, 2008). These systems are then categorized according to their complexity and analysis units, either micro- or macro-level (Head, 2010). In addition, some of the complex problems are classified as poor based on their resistance to clear and easy solutions. The submissive problems were not always easy, but were described as solvable (Ritchey, 2013; Rittel and Webber, 1973). The limits and responsibilities of the problems are not clear. One of the features of these complex social problems mentioned above is the existence of underlying value conflicts (Head and Eisenberg, 2010; Head, 2008; Shön and Rein, 1994).

Strategic planning relates to the proper orientation of the strengths and weaknesses of the organization to take advantage of opportunities arising from its external environment and to minimize threats/problems associated with the external environment (Adeleke vd., 2008). According to Thomas Bateman and Scott Snell, strategic management is a process by which all units of the organization should be involved in the creation or implementation of strategic objectives and strategies. Strategies are the allocation of actions and resources designed to achieve organizational goals. Thompson and Strickland (2003) described the strategic management process as the work of managers to create, implement and execute organization strategies. The benefits of strategies include a position in the right markets, ability to compete successfully, ensure customer satisfaction and achieve high performance. Hofer and I. (1984) The strategic administration is primarily concerned with the creation and development of structural systems necessary to ensure organizational renewal and growth. This process can also be described as strategizing and application processes. Ansoff (1984) called strategic management a systematic approach. This approach is governed by the general government. In addition, this approach should be positioned to ensure that the success of general administration is sustained and warranted, protecting the overall management from potential surprises. In addition, it must ensure that the organization's relations with its environment are consistent. In this definition, the emphasis is placed on the relationship between the organization and the environment.

Sharplin (1985) describes strategic management as the process of creating, implementing and executing plans for the common and persistent issues that remain of importance for the whole organization. In fact, this definition by the researcher can be seen as the most broadly constructed definition of strategic governance. Because this definition states that all the plans and activities that matter to the organization must be considered. Harrison and John (1998) described strategic management as a process in which organizations learn about their internal and external environment, strategically oriented towards the information, and develop applications to help them achieve their goals. The Institute of Strategic Management in Nigeria defines strategic governance as an integrative management process involving all administrative units and employees of an organization (Access Address: www.arabianjbm.com/JPDS_index.php, 01.06.2022). The relevant institution outlines the benefits of strategic management as ensuring that organizations continually assess their environment, ensure proper organization development, facilitate proper organization implementation, ensure continuous control implementation, ensure continuous monitoring of plans, ensure vigilance of all positive/negative changes, create competitive advantage, ensure successful performance.

Strategic management is a process that consistently evaluates and controls the industries the company has been to. In the process, the organization evaluates its competitors, and lays out practices for influence over all current and potential competitors. After this process, they reconsider the strategies they have outlined in specific intervals. The main purpose of this evaluation process is to determine whether strategies are implemented, successful or should be replaced by a new strategy to adapt to changing circumstances (new technology, new competitors, new economic environment, new social, financial, political environment) (Lamb, 1984). Strategic management could also be defined as the organization's goal, and the determination of plans, actions, to achieve that goal. It is a series of administrative decisions and actions that determine an organization's long-term performance. Implementing strategies to help the organization align with its surroundings to achieve goals is another obligation. Lawrence and William (1988) described strategic management as an effective stream of decisions and actions to help achieve corporate goals. Strategic management is the way strategy practitioners determine goals and make strategic decisions. Strategic management is a disciplined approach that explores how any institution will use management principles to determine its goals or missions. Strategic management determines an appropriate target for achieving objectives, recognizes the current opportunities and risks in the environment, and sets out rational methods that can be achieved (Aremu, 2000). Strategic governance is the process of strategizing in the narrowest possible terms, proportional to the missions and visions of organizations. Their missions, visions and strategies play an important role in identifying themselves, providing solutions to problems they face and determining the positions they will assume for their future. Each

of the missions, visions, and strategies must be developed at the beginning of the process of development of the organizations. It is important to note that the three concepts are closely related

3.Tripoli University Overview

Founded in 1957, the University of Tripoli is a non-profit public institution in Tripoli, Libya (with a population of 1,000-5,000,000). The organization's campuses are as follows: Ben Gasher and Janzour. The University of Tripoli, officially recognized by the Libyan Higher Education Authority and the Ministry of Scientific Research, is a university that teaches mixed education to a large number (about 45,000) of students. The University of Tripoli offers pre-bachelor's degrees (i.e. certificates, diplomas, pre-bachelor's or foundation degrees), bachelor's degrees, master's degrees, doctoral degrees, etc. in a variety of working areas, as well as programs that enable officially recognized higher education. With a 63-year history, the university adopted a student-accepting policy through entrance exams. Acceptance rates are around 50-60%, making it a selective institution. International students also have the right to enroll. The University of Tripoli, on the other hand, offers students a variety of academic or non-academic opportunities, including libraries, accommodation, sports facilities and/or activities, financial assistance and/or scholarships, educational and exchange programs abroad, online courses and remote learning opportunities.

Details of the history and strategic plans of the university were posted on the university's website. To take its performance to the next level, the institution has developed a strategic plan intended to help it align itself with world universities. This strategy enabled the University of Tripoli to develop a vision that would help it develop in the years to come. This strategic plan is aimed at building the future of the university on a tradition of radical innovation, accessibility and compatibility embodied by successive generations. The relevant strategic plan focuses on the following key points;

- Strategies and Goals: A strategic plan created by the University aims primarily to provide answers to the questions of those involved.
- Vision: The original approach to research, education and innovation will be adopted. This approach will help to understand how the world is understood, how knowledge is created, shared and how global problems are resolved. It is also seen as a community of staff, students and partners.
- Mission: The University of Tripoli is an intellectual community that is closely following world developments and devoted to changing the world for the better. Our radical and critical thinking has a remarkable ability to integrate our education, research, innovation and initiative into the long-term benefits of humanity. One could say that the university's name change was part of its mission to keep up with the world.
- Objectives: The three objectives of this strategic plan can be laid out in the form of research leadership, transcending borders, and providing public benefits.

The strategic plan aims to inspire and empower research leadership in the first place. The objectives that must be accomplished in order to achieve their objectives can be sorted in this manner. To be the preference of the most talented researchers. To put forward a broad research base. Promoting different research societies. Activate various forms of leadership. Raising research students. To offer early career advancements. Develop cooperation agreements. Being a responsible investigator. To be part of the research community in Libya. To be involved in global research communities. Setting goals that fit the time we're in.

The university is highly regarded for its role as educational and cultural, and has a high importance for social responsibility towards society. So for those who are interested in this space, caring about it will help them achieve more efficient and productive results.

4.The Problem of Research

It is aimed at measuring the performance of the University of Tripoli operating in Libya. This measurement was demonstrated by the field work performed by university staff. On the other hand, it is the fundamental problem of the research that the university has accomplished in strategic planning at what level or in what areas it lacks. The following research questions are useful in describing the fundamental problem of research, based on these statements.

1. Given the staff's perspective, how does strategic planning affect the performance of the units located at Tripoli University?
2. What is the impact of strategic planning on the day-to-day functioning of units at the University of Tripoli and on the activities of administrators?
3. Are there statistically significant differences between the importance of implementing strategic planning and the demographic characteristics of university staff?
4. What are the proposals that could help implement strategic planning at the 4-Tripoli University?

5.Research Hypotheses

The study developed a total of three main hypotheses and each hypothesis has five sub-hypotheses, as follows. The study's hypotheses can be sorted as follows:

- H.1 - There is a statistically significant difference between the variables of strategic planning and the performance of the University of Tripoli.
- H.1.1 - There is a statistically significant difference between the subdimension of strategic planning, flexible planning, and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.
- H.1.2 - A statistically significant difference between realistic management, the subdimension of strategic planning, and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.
- H.1.3 -- There is a statistically significant difference between the subdimension of strategic planning, measurement standards, and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.
- H.1.4 - There is a statistically significant difference between the validation procedures and the University of Tripoli performance variables, which are the subdimension of strategic planning.
- H.1.5 - There is a statistically significant difference between the subdimension of strategic planning, the distinguishing factors and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.
- H.2 - There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' demographic data and the University of Tripoli performance variables.
- H.2.1 - There is a statistically significant difference between the gender of participants and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.
- H.2.2 - There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' ages and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.
- H.2.3 - There is a statistically significant difference between the scientific competences of participants and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.

H.2.4 - There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' work area and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.

H.2.5 - There is a statistically significant difference between the year of study by participants and the performance variables of the University of Tripoli.

H.3 - There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' demographic data and their corporate performance level attitudes variables.

H.3.1 - There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' gender and their corporate performance-level attitudes variables.

H.3.2 - There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' ages and their corporate performance level attitudes variables.

H.3.3 - There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' scientific competences and their corporate level of performance attitudes variables.

H.3.4 - There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' business and enterprise performance level attitudes variables.

H.3.5 - There is a statistically significant difference between the variables of the participants' year of work and their corporate level of performance attitudes.

6. Purpose of Research

The study essentially aims to:

1. Identifying the impact of strategic planning and implementation on the performance of institutions in the education sector.
2. Understanding how and to what degree strategic planning can be implemented at the University of Tripoli and assisting the day-to-day functioning of the administrators involved in the institutions.
3. Identifying differences between demographic data of staff at the University of Tripoli and perceptions of strategic planning.
4. What they're working on is communicating their potential ideas about the institution's strategic planning practices through studies.

7. Scientific Importance of Work

The study of higher education institutions was first examined, and did not involve much research on scientific evidence and field studies. It is primarily important from a scientific perspective. But there are some studies that are based on this, but there are very few qualified studies that actually bring together the two variables in this study. The topic is of great scientific importance in terms of being extremely new and providing the basis for future studies. Another important aspect is that this study has shown that strategic planning also influences the performance of universities.

The study thoroughly investigated various implementation steps of strategic planning. A detailed data set has been obtained regarding the vision and strategic planning activities of the University of Tripoli where the study was conducted. Finally, university administrators have been helped to see the positive effects of strategic planning on performance and help gain awareness of the issue.

This work has been limited to a number of selected units from the University of Tripoli, which has numerous educational institutions.

- Another limitation of the study is that the higher education sector is only interested in the Strategic planning flow. The results therefore apply to higher education institutions.

- Subjectivity is an important factor in qualitative research, it is important to note that qualitative research focuses on the particular situation and experience of survey participants. Therefore, the study's reliance on responses from participants who played different roles in the higher education system has influenced the results of the study. Another limitation of the work pertains to this subject. The study only obtained data through the survey method. Further studies can include observation and in-depth interview methods.

8.Method

The study primarily used descriptive analyzes to determine the relationships between variables and to determine the direction of any relationship that is detected between these variables. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), descriptive statistics allow a researcher to collect, summarize, present and interpret information in a whole way in order to make a statement. The statistical tool for conducting research analyzes can be called basically inference statistics. The analysis methods most favored for determining relationships between variables in the study were the correlation matrix and multiple regression analysis. In the study, the face-to-face polling method was preferred to obtain data. The most important reason for this is that it's economical and also allows for large amounts of data to be collected from a large population. Saunders vd., (2009) proposed this strategy in their study, and another reason for this proposition, except as one of the above reasons, is that it allows researchers to collect data that can be analyzed in quantitative terms using inference statistics. It is also important to note that the implications of the survey method are relatively easy to both clarify and understand.

A journal from the University of Tripoli is first received to provide relevant information in order to achieve research goals. Staff members of the university's respective departments were then identified. The survey has been distributed to eligible personnel through the administrators of the respective units. Participants have been informed in advance of an article about research in order to remove any doubt or mistrust that participants might have about the surveys and research involved. Preface contributors included in an article illustrating how to fill out questionnaires to participate and motivate them to answer questions.

Surveys have been distributed to the relevant personnel through the units. After collecting data from a representative sample using the survey method, the data was organized on the same day to check the lack of data, consistency, and reliability. The relevant survey data was then sequentially organized and logged into the computer environment. This is how you ensure there are no errors, scanning and cleaning of the data. The data was transferred from the computer to the SPSS package program for analysis.

According to Sarantakos (1998), analyzing the data includes the process by which the researcher evaluates the findings, editing the data collected during the study to reach some valid, reasonable and relevant conclusions. The study preferred the descriptive statistical method to present and summarize the biodata, as mentioned previously. Statistical methods for carrying out research analyzes can be sorted as inference statistics, correlation matrix, and multiple regression analysis. And Cooper. (2006) The research method allows a researcher to understand vast amounts of data and effectively communicate important aspects of his work. The software tool for data analysis, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 24), has been used. The resulting qualitative data has been simplified by the content analysis method. The method of content analysis refers to the categorization of data, the identification of keywords, and meaningful interpretation of responses. Saunders. (2009), they define the method of content analysis as organizing the data for easy interpretation under certain key headings after it is categorized. Intel data is provided in prose, and highlights are addressed in the study.

The study sample consisted of a total of 458 employees of the University of Tripoli, Libya. Given that the total number of employees is approximately 4,000 people, 458 attendees are more than 384 people, enough to describe the universe. And the power of data to describe the universe is enough. More than two-thirds (72.3%) of respondents were men. The remaining 27.7% are female participants. More than half of respondents included 58.3% in age groups between 30 and 40 years old. 25.8% of those between 40 and 50 years old. The rest of the sample consists of participants over 50 years of age. The rate is 15.9%.

Testing the First Hypothesis: Strategic Planning has identified a statistically significant relationship between the University of Tripoli's Performance variables. This relationship appears to be at ($p < 0.05$) level. The value of the R² coefficient is 0.472, meaning that it accounts for 47.2% of the total variance caused by the independent variable (Strategic Planning) on the dependent variable (the University of Tripoli's Performance). It should be said that the $f = 407.064$ derived from the results of the ANOVA test is statistically significant. The linear regression model has been found to be better suited than a model with no arguments. The T test value is 20,176. A 1-unit change in the strategic planning scale will result in a co-directional movement of .825 units on the performance scale. This conclusion confirms that the first hypothesis was accepted. So strategic planning has a significant and positive impact on the performance of Tripoli University.

Testing of the first sub-hypothesis: A statistically meaningful relationship has been detected between the underlying dimension of Strategic Planning, Flexible Planning, and the University of Tripoli's Performance variables. This relationship appears to be at ($p < 0.05$) level. The value of the R² coefficient is 0.193, which means that it accounts for 19.3% of the total variance caused by the argument (Flexible Planning) on the dependent variable (the University of Tripoli's Performance). The $F = 108.879$ is statistically significant, derived from the results of the ANOVA test. The T test value is 10,435. A 1-unit change in the flexible planning sub-dimension results in an even-directed movement of .375 units on the performance scale. The results show that the relevant hypothesis was accepted.

Testing the second sub-hypothesis: A statistically meaningful relationship has been detected between Realistic Governance, the lower dimension of Strategic Planning, and the University of Tripoli's Performance variables ($p < 0.05$). The value of the R² coefficient is 0.251, which means that the argument (Realistic Management) explains 25.1% of the total variance caused by the independent variable (University of Tripoli's Performance). The $F = 154.443$ derived from the results of the ANOVA test is statistically significant. The T test value is set at 12,428. A 1-unit change in Realistic Management sub-size also results in a 5-way movement with a .446-unit scale on the performance scale. The results show that the relevant hypothesis was accepted.

Testing the third sub-hypothesis: A statistically meaningful relationship has been detected between the lower dimension of Strategic Planning, the Measurement Standards and the University of Tripoli's Performance variables ($p < 0.05$). The value of the R² coefficient is 0.230, which means that the argument (Measurement Standards) explains 23% of the total variance caused by the dependent (Performance of the University of Tripoli). The $F = 173.356$ is statistically significant, derived from the results of the ANOVA test. The T test value is set to 12,428 ($p < 0.05$ level). The results show that the relevant hypothesis was accepted.

Testing the fourth subhypothesis: A statistically meaningful relationship has been detected between the subdimension of Strategic Planning, the Validation Procedures, and the University of Tripoli's Performance variables ($p < 0.05$). The value of the R² coefficient is 0.226, which means that the argument (Validation Procedures) explains 22.6% of the total variance caused by the dependent (University of Tripoli's Performance). The $F = 134.081$ is statistically significant, derived from the results of the ANOVA test. The T test value is set to 11,579 ($p < 0.05$ level). The results show that the relevant hypothesis was accepted.

Testing the fifth subhypothesis: A statistically meaningful relationship is detected between the subdimension of Strategic Planning, the Distinguishing Factors, and the University of Tripoli's Performance variables ($p < 0.05$). The value of the R2 coefficient is 0.277, which means that the independent variable (Distinguishing Factors) explains 27.7% of the total variance caused by the dependent (University of Tripoli's Performance). The $F = 176,543$ derived from the ANOVA test is statistically significant. The T test value is set to 13,284 ($p < 0.05$ level). The results show that the relevant hypothesis was accepted.

The above analysis results show the total impact of strategic planning on the performance of Tripoli University. On the other hand, it is important to work on determining which sub-dimension of strategic planning has more impact on the performance of the University of Tripoli.

As mentioned earlier, multiple linear regressions were used to investigate which sub-dimension of strategic planning had more impact on the performance of the University of Tripoli. Statistical data shows that the model fits well. The value of the ANOVA test ($f = 81.879$ $p < 0.05$) has been identified as meaningful. Also, all t-test values are meaningful at $p < 0.05$, meaning that all sub-dimensions have a significant impact on the performance of the University of Tripoli. Additionally, these domains have been found to be positively oriented as a result of the resulting multiple. Given the values of beta and t-test, the lower dimension of Realistic Management (0.202) has more impact on the performance of the University of Tripoli than the other four sub-dimensions.

Testing of the Second Hypothesis: "There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' demographic data and the University of Tripoli's strategic planning level variables."

Testing the First Subhypothesis: When data is analyzed, male participants appear to have a higher average score (3,378) than women in attitudes towards strategic planning level. The T-test results were found to be 2,277 at the semantic level of $p < 0.05$, and are meaningful. These results suggest a statistically significant difference between the two groups. Men's strategic planning level perceptions are statistically significantly higher.

Testing the second sub-hypothesis: The ANOVA test was used to determine the differences among survey respondents based on age groups. The f-test value detected is $f = 5.521$. A statistically significant difference has been detected since P is $P < .001$ and $P < .05$. One of the Post Hoc tests, Tukey HSD analysis, was used to determine the age of difference.

The Tukey test was used in Post-Hoc analysis to identify the significant differences between variable groups. The results were found to differ statistically with average scores of participants younger than 30 years of age from 30 to 40, and average scores of participants older than 40 to 50 and 50. Participants under the age of 30 have a more positive attitude towards the level of strategic planning.

Testing the third sub-hypothesis: The ANOVA test was used to identify differences between responses based on the level of education of those surveyed. The f-test value detected is $f = 4,784$. A statistically significant difference has been detected since P is $P < .003$ and $P < .05$. One of the Post Hoc tests, the Tukey HSD analysis, has been used to determine the level of training differences between groups.

The Tukey test was used in Post-Hoc analysis to identify the significant differences between variable groups. Examination of the results found that average scores of participants with technical training and average scores of participants with other bachelor's and post-graduate courses differed statistically. Participants with technical training have a more negative attitude towards the strategic planning level.

Testing the fourth sub-hypothesis: The ANOVA test was used to identify differences between responses based on the positions of those surveyed. The f-test value detected is $f= 4,890$. A statistically significant difference has been detected since P is $P<.000$) and $P<.05$. One of the Post Hoc tests, the Tukey HSD analysis, has been used to determine the level of training differences between groups.

The Tukey test was used in Post-Hoc analysis to identify the significant differences between variable groups. When the results were examined, the average scores of participants in other positions and the average scores of participants in the non-auditor position of manager, manager, department vice president, and department head position were found to differ statistically. Participants in other positions have been found to have a more positive attitude towards the level of strategic planning.

Testing the fifth subordinate hypothesis: The ANOVA test was used to identify differences between responses based on the experience time of those surveyed. The f-test value detected is $f= 8,604$. A statistically significant difference has been detected since P is $P<.000$) and $P<.05$. One of the Post Hoc tests, the Tukey HSD analysis, has been used to determine the length of time the differences are among the groups with experience.

The Tukey test was used in Post-Hoc analysis to identify the significant differences between variable groups. Examination of the results found that the average scores of participants who served for more than 10 years and served less than 5 years differed statistically with average scores of participants between 5 and 10 years. Participants with less than 5 years of service have been found to have a more positive attitude towards the level of strategic planning.

Testing the Third Hypothesis

"There is a statistically significant difference between the participants' demographic data and their institutional performance-level attitudes variables."

Testing the first sub-hypothesis

In attitudes towards corporate performance, male participants appear to have a higher average score (3,340) than women. The T-test results were found to be 2,408 at the meaningful level of $p<0.05$. These results suggest a statistically significant difference between the two groups. Men's perceptions of corporate levels of performance are statistically significantly higher.

Testing the second sub-hypothesis: The ANOVA test was used to determine the differences among survey respondents based on age groups. The f-test value detected is $f= 2.448$. A statistically significant difference has not been detected because $P<.063$) is greater than $P<.05$.

Testing the third sub-hypothesis: The ANOVA test was used to identify differences between responses based on the level of education of those surveyed. The f-test value detected is $f= 0.923$. A statistically significant difference has not been detected, since P does not satisfy the $P<.05$ requirement (.430).

Testing the fourth sub-hypothesis: The ANOVA test was used to identify differences between responses based on the positions of those surveyed. The f-test value detected is $f= 1,000$. A statistically significant difference has not been detected, since P does not satisfy $P<.05$.

Testing the fifth subordinate hypothesis used ANOVA testing to determine differences between responses based on the experience time of those surveyed. The f-test value detected is $f= 2.319$. No statistically significant difference has been detected since P value (100) did not satisfy $P<.05$.

These results showed that strategic planning at the University of Tripoli had an impact on the performance of the institution. All five sub-dimensions of strategic planning are heavily influenced by the University of Tripoli's institutional performance. In addition, statistically significant differences have been detected between the participants' demographic data and their attitudes towards the level of strategic planning applied at the University of Tripoli. However, no statistically significant difference in their attitudes toward enterprise performance has been detected. Participants may be interpreted as being homogenous in their attitudes towards corporate performance.

9. Result

Strategic planning is a vital part of helping Libya's existing universities become better in the future. On the other hand, the confidence environment and political conditions in Libya are a factor that can delay the adoption of the universities' strategic planning. However, studies have shown that the competition between universities will increase even further if the trust environment in Libya is established.

Strategic planning will enable universities existing in Libya to compete with foreign universities that are lower than they are, and even hold a rank among universities. In addition, the concept of globalization will create difficulties for universities at low levels, and will lead to the emergence of the principle of competition.

In her study, Karen E. Hinton (2012) argues that modern strategic plans consist of several components, each serving a different purpose. These components are characterized as stand-alone or grouped planning tools. The objectives of the planning process are to ensure that the components are synchronized and to support each other mutually.

This study found that strategic planning had a positive effect on the performance of the University of Tripoli. Participants in the study argue that universities are service-oriented organizations and that their strategic planning should be carried out in different applications than corporate organizations. Dooley. (2000) according to their study, they found that strategy applications relate to many organizational factors, particularly performance. Rahma Zuaibi (2014) found a statistically meaningful relationship between strategic planning and performance level in a similar study.

A comprehensive and critical assessment has been made to better understand the current situation and role of tertiary services in Libya. It is important to note that strategic planning was first developed for educational institutions (Piorun, 2011). Kariuki1 and. (2016) in their study, they found that strategy applications had a great effect on school performance. It is understood that the missions, visions, goals and values of schools are clearly documented and hung within the school. The importance of the link between strategic planning and evaluation to make an institution effective is also recognized by the researchers (Holloway vd., 2006). Consequently, one can say that strategic planning practices have been adopted and can be used in both the

public and private sectors (Rowley and Sherman, 2004). In 2014, he stated that his perception of the importance of strategic planning and research on the subject was extremely poor. It is important to remember that strategic plans lead people and/or organizations to think about the future.

In a recent study, Bedran and Abukhshem (2020) emphasized the importance of strategic planning in undergraduate studies at the University of Tripoli. The results also revealed the role financial and human resources played in the success of the strategic planning process. The reasons include the weak beliefs of strategic planning by some Tripoli University administrators, as well as the cumbersome bureaucracy which exists in administrative work.

Elhwuegi. (2013), after the political changes in Libya, i.e. after 2011, he proposed the implementation of strategic plans for the University of Tripoli. The proposed strategic plan aims to deliver a high-quality education system that can help develop human skills, competing at regional and international levels, with a sense of belonging to the country and institutional principles. Obstacles that may arise in this process include the dilapidation of bureaucracy, the relaxation of administrative structure and the reduced quality of public services.

As regards literature screening and the controversy surrounding it, strategic planning for better organization performance is vital. Therefore, the relationship of each subdimension of strategic planning to organization performance has been tested in this study. This study provides advice on how strategic planning can help make better decisions in the future.

The success of any institution is very important for the sake of continuity of the institution. Without good performance and high profitability, it is impossible for the institution to survive. The study covered two concepts, namely "strategic planning" and "business performance". The study found that the University of Tripoli has a high level of implementation of strategic planning stages, as well as a high level of performance at the University of Tripoli. The concept of strategic planning also has a statistically significant effect on the performance of the University of Tripoli. The results can be sorted in the following order:

- 1st Strategic planning has a statistically significant impact on the performance of the University of Tripoli.
- 2nd The lower dimension of flexible planning has a statistically significant effect on the performance level of the University of Tripoli.
- 3rd The lower dimension of realistic governance has a statistically significant impact on the performance level of the University of Tripoli.
- 4th The lower standard size has a statistically significant effect on the performance level of the University of Tripoli.
- 5th The lower dimension of validation procedures has a statistically significant impact on the performance level of the University of Tripoli.
- 6th The distinctive factor subsize has a statistically significant effect on the performance level of the University of Tripoli.
- 7th The subdimension of realistic governance has more impact on the performance of the University of Tripoli than on the other four sub-dimensions.
- 8th Male participants have a higher average of strategic planning level perceptions than female participants.
- 9th Participants in the age group under 30 receive higher and meaningful average scores than participants of other ages.
- 10th Participants with technical training have lower strategic planning attitudes than those with other educational levels.

- 11th Participants in other positions on the strategic planning scale have a more positive view of strategic planning.
- 12th Participants with 12,100 years and more work experience and less than 5 years of business experience have a more positive view of strategic planning.
- 13th Male participants have a higher average of enterprise performance than female participants.
- 14th No statistically significant difference has been detected between corporate perceptions of performance given the age of participants.
- 15th No statistically significant difference between participants' perceptions of corporate performance has been detected given their education levels.
- 16th No statistically significant difference has been detected between the perceptions of corporate performance given the participants' positions.
- 17th No statistically significant difference in business performance perceptions has been detected given the length of time participants spend in the profession.

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